

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PARENTAL PARENTING AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIAL BEHAVIOR EMOTIONAL CHILDREN WITH AUTISM IN LANGSA CITY, ACEH INDONESIA

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Abstract

Background: Autism is a complex developmental disorder, which is related to communication, social interaction and imagination activities, the number of children with autism is increasing in the United States so that boys are four times more likely to be diagnosed with autism disorder and in 2015, there were 873,000 children between the ages of 3 and 17 diagnosed with autism. The WHO in 2018 reported that 1 in 160 children had autism spectrum disorder. Many parents do not understand how to provide optimal parenting to children with autism, because lack of knowledge about parenting, causes children to continue to suffer from autism, so parents have no hope for their child's future. **Objective:** To determine the relationship between parental parenting and the development of socio-emotional behavior of autistic children in Langsa city. **Methods:** The quantitative study used a *Cross Sectional* design with a Correlative hypothesis with 34 respondents of parents (mothers) who have children 2-5 years old. **Results:** The results of this study showed that most parents showed poor parenting 73.5% and good parenting 26.5%, while as many as 85.3% showed poor child behavior and 14.7% good child behavior. Bivariate analysis shows a p value $< \alpha$ 0.05 so it can be concluded that there is a significant relationship between parenting patterns and the social emotional behavior of autistic children in Langsa City.

Keywords: Autism, Behavior, Emotional, Parenting, Social.

1. INTRODUCTION

Autism is a complex developmental disorder and one of five disorders of Pervasive Development Disorder (PDD). People with autism disorder will experience delays in the fields of cognitive, behavioral and social interaction. This disorder is caused by neurobiological factors that can be detected at the age of less than 3 years. Another term for these autistic children is "exceptional children" Data from the WHO in 2018 reported that 1 in 160 children have autism spectrum disorder. Autism spectrum disorder starts from childhood and persists into adolescence and adulthood. The prevalence of autism spectrum disorder worldwide in the United States in 2018 increased from other countries to 168:10,000 children. The latest data regarding the prevalence of autism in Indonesia shows a significant increase. Deputy Minister of Health of the Republic of Indonesia, dr. Dante Saksono Harbuwono, revealed that currently it is estimated that around 2.4 million children in Indonesia experience autism spectrum disorder (ASD). This estimate is in line with data from the Central Statistics Agency (BPS) which states that out of Indonesia's total population of around 270.2 million people, there are around 3.2 million children with autism.[1]

The Data Center for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC, 2018) states that the prevalence of autism increased from 1 in 150 population in 2000 to 1 in 59 in 2014. ASD affects boys more, with a prevalence of 1:37, while in girls it is 1:151. Referring to the prevalence data, Indonesia, which has a population of 237.5 million with a population growth rate of 1.14%, is estimated to have 4 million people with ASD. Anek Nanggroe Extraordinary School (SLB) and Cinta Mandiri Extraordinary School (SLB) Lhoksemawe City, Aceh Province, calculated in 2019-2020 at SLB Anek Nanggroe there were 16 elementary school level children who experienced autism, and

SLB Cinta Mandiri in 2019-2020 there were 15 elementary school level children who experienced autism.[2]

The cause of autism is suspected to be due to neurobiological disorders in the central nervous system, namely genetic factors, impaired growth of brain cells in the fetus, digestive disorders, heavy metal poisoning during pregnancy and autoimmune disorders. One of the causes of autism is genetic factors and environmental influences, viruses, immune function disorders, brain organ disorders, gastrointestinal disorders and exposure to heavy metals when the child is in the womb, such as lead, mercury, cadmium, infantile spasma, congenital rubella, tuberous sclerosis, cerebral lipidosis and fragile X chromosome anomalies. One of the factors that affect a child's attitude and behavior is the parenting style of parents and family. Parenting has a very important role for the development of moral behavior in children because the first basis of moral behavior is obtained by children from within the home, namely from their parents. In his research, Riandini divided parenting in children into three forms, namely Authoritative (Democratic), Indulgent (Permissive), and Authoritarian (Authoritarian).[3]

Authoritative parenting is a parenting style that tends to cause children to have friendly nature, have confidence, be able to control (self-control), be polite, willing to cooperate, have high curiosity, have clear goals or directions, are achievement-oriented, and dare to speak up. Permissive parenting is that parents educate children freely, children are considered adults (young), they are given the widest possible leeway to do whatever they want. Everything children do is right and does not need to be reprimanded, directed (guidance) so that children tend to have characteristics of being impulsive and aggressive, like to be rebellious, lack confidence, like to dominate, are not clear in their direction, and their achievements are low [3]. Authoritarian parenting is a parenting style that is full of restrictions and punishment (violence) by the way parents impose their will, so that parents have full control in controlling their children but still give affection to their children.[4]

Parents who have children with autism will experience more complex problems in the formation of personality, behavior and fulfillment of children's needs. So that with the increasing age of children with autism, parents must make adjustments, especially in meeting the daily needs of their children, such as in terms of providing parenting and as parents must be able to understand the development of children who suffer from autism so that children do not have prolonged problems, parenting styles that can be given to children with autism, for example by communicating slowly and without offending, giving clear commands to children with autism so that they are easily understood by children.[5] [16]

Of the three types of parenting, the impact on child development is also different. Seeing the lack of parental knowledge about parenting styles given to children and the relationship between parenting and social-emotional behavior in children with autism are different, researchers are interested in researching "The Relationship between Parenting Parenting Styles and Social-Emotional Behavior of Autistic Children in Langsa City". The aim of this research is to determine the relationship between parenting patterns and the development of socio-emotional behavior in autistic children in the city of Langsa.

2. METHODOLOGY

This study is an associative study with a correlational hypothesis. The design used in this study is Cross Sectional with the number of respondents 34 mothers who have children aged 2-5 years with autism disorders in Langsa City. The sampling technique used in this study is total sampling.

The instrument in this study uses a questionnaire about parenting and behavior of autistic children Data collection through filling out a questionnaire carried out by 34 respondents using an nominal scale, while waiting for their child to do therapy at the Autism Service Center. Data analysis using a computer program with the results of the analysis using univariate analysis using frequency distribution and bivariate analysis was carried out to see the relationship between parenting style and behavior of autistic children using the Chi Square test, $\alpha < 0.05$ and Confidence Interval (CI) 95%. Chi-square is a statistical test used to test the difference between observed and expected distributions. This test can also be used to test the relationship between categorical variables.[6]

3. RESULTS

3.1 Univariate Analysis

3.1.1 Distribution of Parenting

Parenting Style	n	%
Good Parenting	9	26,5
Poor Parenting	25	73,5
Total	34	100

Based on table 3.1, it shows that out of 34 respondents, the majority had poor parenting as many as 25 respondents (73.5%) and 9 respondents (26.5%) had good parenting.

3.1.2 Social-Emotional Behavior Disorders of Autistic Children

Socio-Emotional Behavior of Autistic Children	n	%
Good social-emotional behavior	5	14,7
Social-emotional behavior Less	29	85,3
Total	34	100

Based on table 3.2, it shows that of the 34 respondents, the majority have poor social-emotional behavior, as many as 29 respondents (85.3%) and those who have good social-emotional behavior, as many as 5 respondents (14.7%).

3.2 Bivariate Analysis

3.2.1 The Relationship of Parenting Styles to Social Behavior

Emotional Autistic Children.

Variable	P Value	Relationship Intimacy
Parenting Style Children's Social Emotional Behavior	0,001	0,563

Based on table 3.3 above, the results of the statistical test using the chi square test obtained a p value of $0.001 < \alpha 0.05$, which means that there is a significant relationship between the dependent variable of the child's social emotional behavior variable and the independent variable of parental parenting patterns. Based on the results of the close relationship test between the two variables, the results obtained were 0.563, which means that the relationship between the parenting pattern variable and the Social Emotional Behavior variable of autistic children is included in the category of having a moderate relationship.

4. DISCUSSION

This study was conducted to determine the relationship between parenting patterns and the socio-emotional behavior of autistic children in Langsa City. The total number of samples used was 34 respondents from mothers who have children aged 2-5 years. Parenting styles have an important role in influencing the development of social and emotional behavior in children with autism. Various studies have examined how different types of parenting impact these aspects. Overall, research shows that parenting styles have a significant influence on the social and emotional behavior of children with autism. Democratic parenting tends to have a positive impact, while authoritarian and permissive parenting can hinder this development. Therefore, it is important for parents to implement parenting patterns that support optimal development of children with autism. [20]

Based on the research conducted, parental parenting has a significant relationship with the social-emotional behavior of autistic children. This can be seen from the parenting style that tends to be lacking, which is 73.5%, with social-emotional behavior which is also very lacking, which is

85.3%. The results of this analysis are strengthened by the results of a previous study by Silaban (2014), which stated that parental parenting affects the behavior of autistic children who follow therapy at the Tali Kasih Medan Foundation.[7] [15]

This research found that democratic parenting is associated with better social interactions in children with autism. As many as 41.9% of parents implemented a democratic parenting style, and of this number, 24.3% of children showed good social interactions. Statistical analysis shows a p value of 0.000 and an odds ratio (OR) of 3.260 with a 95% confidence interval (1.246-8.533), which indicates a significant relationship between democratic parenting and positive social interactions in children with autism. Olinda (2021) stated that parenting patterns parents are a way used by parents to interact with children which includes, giving rules, reward, punishment, reward attention, and providing responses to child behavior. Jetti and Manan (2022) stated that the parenting style of parents This is a habit of parents leading, nurturing and guiding children in a family.[8] [21]

The results of Rohmiana's research show that there is an influence between parenting patterns on the social emotional development of children aged 4-5 years at Al-Hidayah V Kindergarten, with a regression coefficient value of 1,000 and a t test showing that the t count is greater than the t table ($2,446 > 2,179$) which means H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. Therefore, parenting styles have an influence on the social emotional development of children aged 4-5 years at Al-Hidayah V Kindergarten.[9][10]

Behavior in autistic children is indeed formed by itself which is caused by disturbances in the nervous system, body metabolism and intestinal wall in children. Such behavior can be changed according to the behavior expected by society in general. Because the therapy used in autistic children is behavioral therapy, which is a method used in their daily teaching and learning practices, which aims to minimize children's shortcomings and maximize children's potential so that they can develop optimally. So that the behavior of autistic children can be accepted by the environment and society in general and children can adapt to a normal environment. So parents play a very important role in shaping the child's behavior into behavior that is in accordance with expectations, because parents are the closest people to children.[11][3]

The family is the main person who should support the development of autistic children, although often the birth and existence of autistic children cause problems in the family. The stage of not being able to accept, shock, disappointment, abandonment, distrust, and irritation and anger are often experienced by parents in autistic children. The situation of not being able to accept the condition of autistic children makes the parenting style of autistic children as a result not optimal. In fact, it is often an emotional problem in the family. Attention from parents is needed for autistic children, especially mothers involved in taking care of autistic children throughout the day [12][14]. Parents can provide good parenting for autistic children by making a daily routine schedule for children, namely cutting time related to the electronic world [13].

Research assumes the importance of the role of parents in the social development of autistic children. It is emphasized that the parenting style applied by parents greatly influences children's ability to interact socially. Proper parenting can help autistic children develop better social skills. [19]

5. CONCLUSIONS

The results of the study entitled The Relationship between Parenting Patterns and the Development of Social Emotional Behavior of Autistic Children in Langsa City obtained a p-value of 0.001, which means that there is a relationship between parenting patterns and the development of social emotional behavior of autistic children in Langsa City. Based on the results of the test of the closeness of the relationship between the two variables, the results obtained were 0.563, which means that the relationship between the parenting pattern variable and the Social Emotional Behavior variable of autistic children is included in the moderate relationship category. The researcher really hopes that further research can explore more deeply the types of parenting patterns and other factors that can influence the Development of Social Emotional Behavior of Autistic Children. [17] [18]

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